

VAPOUR PHASE CHLORINATION OF ETHANOL UNDER
SILENT ELECTRIC DISCHARGE.* PART I.
QUALITATIVE STUDIES

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Chlorination of ethanol has been carried out in vapour phase under silent electrical excitation. The products obtained have been found to contain ethyl acetate, di- and trichloroacetaldehydes, trichloroacetaldehyde alcoholate, paraldehyde, mono-, di- and trichloroacetaldehyde acetals, 1:2-di- and 1:2:2-trichlorodiethyl ethers, hexachlorethane, HCl and some organic acids besides unchanged ethanol.

A large amount of work has been reported in the literature on the chlorination of ethanol in liquid phase, a process exploited commercially for the manufacture of chloral and allied compounds. The present author has studied this reaction in the vapour phase under the silent electrical excitation. This communication deals with a detailed qualitative study of the products formed.

EXPERIMENTAL

The glass apparatus and electrical circuit are shown in Fig. 1 which is self explanatory. A few points may, however, be mentioned. The discharge tube consists of a Siemens' type all-glass ozonizer (O) with the following dimensions :

External diameter of the outer tube	=	12 mm.
Internal " " " " "	=	9
External " " " inner "	=	6
Internal " " " " "	=	4
Average length of the ozonizer	=	350 (approx.)

The two feeding nozzles, N and N' (for alcohol vapour and chlorine respectively), were drawn into fine jets so as to avoid back diffusion, and N was fitted internally into the feeder in such a way that any liquid trickling down the ozonizer was collected in a separate receiving bulb (R.B.) and could not go back to the boiling flask (B.F.). Size of the feeder was kept minimum possible and asbestos wound round it to avoid condensation of alcohol vapour. The uncondensed gases emerging from U-tube (U), cooled in powdered ice, were passed through a water-filled Dreschel bottle (not shown in the fig.) to absorb water-soluble gases and then bubbled through a strong solution of sodium hydroxide (to remove unchanged chlorine) before being sucked up by a water filter pump which helped to maintain a uniform flow of gases through the system; a safety bottle was interposed before each bubbler.

* A brief report of preliminary investigations has already been published by Malhotra and Trivedi. (*Curr. Sci.*, 1955, 35, 337).

FIG. 1

H.T. High tension transformer.

B.T. Bell transformer.

G. Galvanometer.

D.F. Dropping funnel.

O. Ozoniser.

J. Water jacket.

R.B. Receiving bulb*

B.F. Boiling flask.

U. U-tube.

F. Feeder.

N, N'. Feeding nozzles.

Alcohol was fed from the dropping funnel (D.F.) at the rate of 4 c.c./hour and chlorine, preheated to 80° (approx.), passed at 6 c.c./sec. (as measured by a flow-meter, not shown in the fig.). The ozoniser was maintained at $80-90^\circ$ and a steady discharge was passed through it at 2.6 kV (500 cycles/sec. A.C), a potential slightly higher than the threshold potential required for the dielectric breakdown of the gases.

Products collected.—A yellowish brown viscous liquid with a sharp pungent smell (of HCl) was obtained by mixing the products collected in the U-tube (U) and the bulb (R.B.). It was strongly acidic and fumed in moist air. The entire product, after neutralisation with excess of pure calcium carbonate, was fractionated repeatedly and the fractions identified by usual methods. Starting from 100^o c.c. of the products, the amounts of different fractions and the compounds identified in each have been recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Analysis of the products.

Volume of discharge products taken = 100 c.c.

Temp. range.	Volume.	Compounds identified.
1. Below 78° (mainly 76-78°)	8 c.c.	Ethyl acetate + ethanol
2. 78-80°	35	Ethanol
3. 80-85°	4	Ethanol + dichloroacetaldehyde
4. 89-94°	4	Dichloroacetaldehyde
5. 96-100°	6	Trichloroacetaldehyde (chloral)
6. 114-116°	1	Trichloroacetaldehyde alcoholate
7. 120-150°	0.5	Paraldehyde*
8. 156-164°	10	Monochloroacetaldehyde acetal + 1 : 2-dichlorodiethyl ether* + 1 : 2 : 2-trichlorodiethyl ether*
9. 175-185°	35	Dichloroacetaldehyde acetal
10. Residue	1	Trichloroacetaldehyde acetal

* Confirmatory tests for these compounds could not be performed for want of sufficient material.

Free Acidity.—Several runs of the discharge products (8 c.c. each), collected at different potentials, were diluted (volume made up to 100 c.c.) and separately analysed volumetrically for H⁺ and Cl⁻ ions to ascertain if the acidic nature of the products was due entirely to HCl or some other acids were present beside it. The normalities of these two ions in the different runs have been recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Estimation of H⁺ and Cl⁻ ions.

Sr No.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
H ⁺ (normality)	0.5601	0.4849	0.4301	0.5261	0.4446	0.4823	0.5924	0.3965
Cl ⁻ (")	0.5520	0.4630	0.4244	0.5058	0.4308	0.4741	0.5733	0.3810
Diff. (")	0.0081	0.0219	0.0057	0.0203	0.0138	0.0082	0.0192	0.0155

The value of H⁺ ion normality being invariably higher than that of Cl⁻ ions, the presence of some other acids, possibly organic carboxylic acids, was indicated, and confirmed by spot tests, viz., the two ferric chloride tests (Fiegel, Anger and Freuden, *Mikrochem.*, 1934, 16, 18; cf. Davidson, *J. Chem. Ed.*, 1940, 17, 81; Fiegel, "Spot Tests", 3rd ed., 1947, p. 399) and the lanthanum nitrate test (Kruger and Tschirch, *Ber.*, 1929, 62, 2770; 1930, 63, 826; *Mikrochem.*, 1930, 8, 218). The indigo test with *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde (Fiegel, Sanchez and Zappert, *Mikrochem.*, 1935, 17, 165), however, was negative, thus indicating the absence of acetic acid. As no specific tests for chlorine-substituted acetic acids were available, no distinction could be made between them.

Presence of Hexachloroethane.—Distillation of the discharge products without neutralisation left a dark residue which on standing deposited white camphoraceous smelling crystals. Such crystals, obtained from about 100 c.c. of the products,

were washed with water and recrystallised from aqueous alcohol. The solid melted at 186° (in a sealed tube) and did not lower the m.p. of an authentic sample of hexachloroethane (m.p. $186-87^{\circ}$ in a sealed tube) (Huntress, "Organic Chlorine Compounds", John Wiley, 1948, p. 439)).

Analysis of Water Washings.—Water washings of the exit gases, after being neutralised with calcium carbonate, were distilled and the fraction boiling below 98° was treated with a large excess of anhydrous copper sulphate and extracted with ether. The solvent was evaporated off and the residue (about 0.5 c.c.) was identified as chloral. The rest of the water washings distilled at $98^{\circ}-100^{\circ}$ and consisted mostly of water.

Further work and the mechanism of this reaction will appear in a later communication.

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